

PATHOMORPHOLOGY OF THE LIVER IN DECEASED PATIENTS IN THE EARLY PERIOD OF POSTPARTUM OBSTETRIC HEMORRHAGE

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ABSTRACT

In the early period of postpartum obstetric hemorrhage (mainly within 2–6 hours), acute hemodilution and hypovolemia lead to massive anemia in the liver tissue, resulting in the development of "shock liver." This involves altered histotectonics of hepatic lobules, isolated hepatocytes, hyaline thrombi in hemocapillaries, and focal sludging phenomenon in erythrocytes. A characteristic feature is the scarcity of necrotic foci alongside massive hyaline droplet and hydropic dystrophy of hepatocytes. This is driven by an intracellular protein-energy deficit caused by a sharp decrease in blood protein levels and the massive release of proteins from hepatocyte cytoplasm into the vascular lumen.

Relevance of the Problem: Liver pathologies developing during pregnancy account for an average of 0.1% of all liver diseases worldwide, with 88% manifesting as liver failure. This contributes to 68.3% of maternal mortality from this pathology. According to A.R. Hart et al. (2009), the incidence of liver pathologies during pregnancy has increased 5.5-fold in the last 20 years, with a mortality rate exceeding 50%. Data from the USA, UK, and Europe show a rate of 33 cases per 100,000 pregnancies, often leading to acute pancreatitis (88%) and high mortality (12–48%). In the Russian Federation, cases rose from 25–50 per 100,000 in 2010 to over 180 in 2023–2024. In CIS countries, these are often recorded as exacerbations of chronic hepatitis (85–172 cases per 100,000).

Discussion and Results: While "shock liver" is a common morphological feature in acute hemorrhagic conditions, in the early postpartum period of obstetric hemorrhage, pre-existing fatty hepatitis is also involved. Microscopic findings include large and medium droplet dystrophy and the accumulation of bile pigments in the cytoplasm. Significant findings include isolated hepatocytes, necrobiosis in cells with fatty dystrophy, and infiltration around the triads (histiocytes, fibroblasts, Kupffer cells).

Massive expansion of sinusoids, particularly the space of Disse, confirms the accumulation of toxic substances and impaired utilization. The presence of fatty inclusions and bile pigments in perilobular hepatocytes indicates the development of rapid intrahepatic cholestasis. Within 2–4 hours, numerous monocellular necroses, diapedetic hemorrhages, and focal infiltration of lymphocytes and macrophages are observed in the liver lobules. This confirms the deepening

of the process, the formation of "shock cells," and irreversible changes in the histoarchitectonics of the liver.

Furthermore, the onset of HELLP syndrome in these morphological changes acts as an initiator of DIC syndrome, explained by a sharp decline in blood rheological parameters. These changes often manifest as hypocoagulation, plasmatic swelling of the stroma, and rapid formation of interstitial edema in the triads, while liver enzyme changes may not be detectable in blood tests for the first 2–4 hours.

Conclusion

In the early stage of postpartum obstetric hemorrhage, one of the primary changes occurs in the liver tissue. In addition to the "shock liver" presentation, findings include intrahepatic cholestasis, necrosis of hepatocytes rich in bile pigments, and hepatocytes undergoing medium and large droplet fatty dystrophy. This proves that acute processes in the liver, beyond the direct impact of bleeding, are intrinsically linked to the pregnancy itself.

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